

Ego Network Structures in Multilayer Online Social Networks

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Abstract

Personal networks, i.e., the ensemble of social relationships that an individual entertains with other people, have received significant attention from researchers, and Dunbar's ego network model has proved to be a valuable tool for understanding their characteristics, both for offline and online interactions. Most of the studies in the literature are focused on single-layer ego networks, where relationships are treated as if they all belong to the same context. However, studies on multi-layer networks have recently highlighted the importance of considering the different dimensions of real-life networks. In this study, we bridge the gap between the literature on ego networks and that on multilayer networks by introducing the concept of *multilayer ego networks*. Our goal is to assess whether multilayer ego networks feature the same structural regularities observed in single-layers ego networks and to investigate the role that the different layers play in how people interact with each other. To this aim, we leverage a dataset extracted from Reddit, and we treat each subreddit as a different layer of the social network. How results show (i) that multilayer ego networks are self-similar, (ii) that egos distribute their cognitive efforts proportionally across their layers, and (iii) that egos accommodate multiple layers by adapting the outermost circles without significantly affecting the innermost ones.

Keywords: online social networks, ego networks, multilayer networks, Reddit

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1. Introduction

Online social media has been increasingly important in the way of communicating with each other for the last decades. With easy access to the Internet, the number of people that incorporate Online Social Networks (OSNs) into their daily life has drastically increased. As of January 2021, there are 4.2 billion (53.6% of the global population) worldwide active social media users¹, of which 98.8% accessing via mobile devices. Acceleration in the usage of mobile devices and easy access to social media pushed the cyber-physical convergence phenomenon. The interaction among physical world objects, humans, and cyberspace fostered the generation and exchange of data between the cyber and physical worlds. Thus, the data produced online introduced new opportunities for researchers to understand human interactions. Social media creates a huge volume of data, and the increase in cyber-physical convergence gives researchers the opportunity to use it to understand and explain existing patterns across online and offline interactions. On the one hand, online social media users create new virtual relationships that do not exist in offline networks. On the other hand, they carry their existing relationships to these platforms where communication is faster and sometimes easier than communicating with these peers in the physical world. These new methods of managing our relationships are also shaping our understanding of human interactions. The vast majority of the theories about human interactions and behaviors were formulated for the offline world and based on data about offline interactions. We can now test these theories on this converged cyber-physical world leveraging large-scale data from OSNs, which became a “social microscope” into our cyber-physical relationships.

In this work, we consider a human behavioral model that is well-established in the anthropology literature, and that goes under the name of *social brain hypothesis* [1]. The theory behind the model postulates that humans can meaningfully interact with at most, on average, 150 people (the Dunbar’s number) and that these 150 people can be arranged in circles of different levels of intimacy [2]. The number of relationships an ego can maintain is in fact limited by the information-processing capacity of the primate brain [1] and temporal constraints [3, 4]. These results are rooted in studies of the primate brains and of how humans allocated their cognitive resources to social inter-

¹(accessed on March 28, 2021) <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2021-global-overview-report>

actions. This social structure with concentric circles is typically represented with a graph abstraction known as *ego network model*. An ego network is a collection of relationships between an individual (*ego*) and its peers (*alters*). It is a local graph with the ego at the center and links connecting the ego with its alters (alter-to-alter relationships are not present). Ego networks are one of the important structures to analyze social behavior. An active relationship is defined as a tie between two individuals having at least one contact per year. These 150 relationships are hierarchically clustered into groups (the number of alters per group being 5, 15, 45, 150, respectively, according to studies on offline networks [1, 2]). Recently, similar findings have been confirmed for our online interactions [5], where the model has been extended with an additional social circle with 1.5 alters (which was uncovered thanks to the availability of large-scale data for online interactions). The Dunbar's ego network structure is illustrated in Figure 1. This model will be discussed in detail in Section 2 and Section 4. An interesting regularity in Dunbar's ego network structure is that the ratio of consecutive circles (known as *scaling ratio*) is typically around 3 both for offline and online social networks [1, 6].

Figure 1: Dunbar's ego network model.

The ego network model introduced above is basically a weighted local subgraph of a complex social network among users. As research on complex networks has matured, it has become clear that the majority of real-life networks are multidimensional. Researchers have started to underline the importance of not neglecting the subsystems within networks since neglecting them may result in incorrect inferences. In fact, ignoring the natural organization of social networks may lead us to oversimplify the conceptual-

ization of the system [7], and this may result in misleading representations. The subsystems within a complex system, which are structured as levels of the system, have been a part of the discussions in social sciences much before them in computational sciences. For example, in [8], the view of a city has been proposed as a network of networks. However, until the last decade, the representation of subsystems in the networks has not received much attention. The use of multilayer networks aims to fill this gap by providing a generalized representation of complex systems or complex social phenomena (e.g., biological structures and interactions, information spread through social interactions) that are observed in different domains [9]. These abstractions are generally based on the heterogeneity of the actors, the relationships between them, and the interdependency between these relationships [9]. A multilayer network consists of subnetworks (referred to as *layers*) that are connected with inter-layer relationships. Each subnetwork includes actors/individuals and relationships between them, i.e., intra-layer relationships. Each layer/subnetwork may consist of different actors, and/or the same actors linked by a different type of relationships, or a different context. For example, as individuals, we are generally part of more than one community. Each community has a different context based on the common interest of its members. Thus, in order to comprehensively characterize how humans interact with each other, we should understand how humans interact within and across the different communities they belong to, i.e., within and across the multiple layers of their social network.

The goal of this work is to discover the multilayer properties of ego networks. To the best of our knowledge, only a few studies have examined how we allocate our cognitive resources through different contexts (the only exception being papers on multichannel communications [10, 11, 12], which we discuss in Section 2). As it is known that ego network structures are determined by cognitive constraints, in this paper, we aim at understanding how these constraints shape our multilayer ego network, i.e., the ego networks we build in the various social contexts where are embedded. How we allocate our cognitive resources for the same peers in different contexts may be different. We may have frequent interactions with a peer in one context and sporadic interactions in another one. Besides the direct effect of the context on individual relationships, there may be higher-level behavioral patterns that are dependent on context. We may be extremely involved in a specific context, much less so in another one. So, one question is whether we maintain the same behavioral patterns through different contexts, even if we allocate a

different “effort” to each of them. In other words, do we shape our ego networks similarly in the contexts for which we allocate most and least cognitive resources? Specifically, we tackle the following research questions:

RQ#1: Do we structure our ego networks similarly in the different communities we are a part of?

RQ#2 Do we allocate the same cognitive effort to the same intimacy group in the different communities?

RQ#3 If you engage with many communities, does your ego network size increase or decrease?

In the scope of this study, we use a Reddit dataset. Reddit is a collection of subreddits where each subreddit is a context/community about a specific topic. We extract an ego network per subreddit for each Reddit user. Thus, each subreddit of a user corresponds to a layer in the multilayer network. The key findings of the study are the following:

- Multilayer ego networks are **self-similar**: their structural properties are very stable, regardless of the number of “significant” subreddits (i.e., those taking up considerable cognitive efforts) for the ego or their ranking, and concentrated between 2 and 5 social circles that is quite similar to the general ego network model.
- Egos distribute their **cognitive efforts proportionally across their layers** instead of assigning a fixed effort to the top-ranked subreddit and allocating whatever is left to the other subreddits.
- Egos accommodate multiple layers by **adapting the outermost circles without significantly affecting the innermost ones**. Indeed, the innermost circle is small and its size has little variability. Vice versa, the outermost circle tends to grow with the ranking of the subreddit, i.e., with the cognitive efforts allocated to the layer. However, its size also decreases as the number of “significant” subreddits for the ego grows.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, we overview the related literature on ego networks and multilayer networks. In Section 3, we discuss how we collected and preprocessed the Reddit dataset we use for

our analysis. In Section 4, we describe the standard ego network model, and we propose its multilayer version. In Sections 5 and 6, we apply the single-layer and multilayer ego network models to our Reddit dataset, and we investigate their properties. We conclude the paper in Section 7.

2. Related Work

2.1. Ego Networks

According to the social brain hypothesis, the number of active relationships that an ego can maintain is limited by the information-processing capacity of the human brain [1, 2] and by time [2]. In [1], the anthropologist R. Dunbar has predicted that, on average, the number of important relationships an individual can maintain is around 150. These 150 relationships are arranged in a structural hierarchy as shown in Figure 1. Dunbar’s model and the associated limitation on the number of significant relationships have been supported by evidence both in offline and online social networks. In [13], an experiment has been carried out considering face-to-face interactions of individuals recorded through a questionnaire. The authors have shown that there are constraints on the number of relationships and their intimacy that an ego can maintain. In addition to face-to-face interactions, the social capacity limitations of the human brains on the number of relationships have been shown for other offline world communication mediums such as letters, Christmas letters, in [2] and phone calls in [3]. Besides offline networks, the validity of Dunbar’s model has been shown for online relationships as well. Even though it may seem like we are establishing and maintaining much more relationships on online platforms, the studies show that similar limitations exist for online relationships since we are using the same cognitive resources. One of the first empirical evidences for online social networks supporting Dunbar’s model has been shown in [14] where authors show that the results of Twitter data analysis are in agreement with Dunbar’s number. In [5], not just the Dunbar’s number but also the configuration of the hierarchical structure of the model has been shown in online networks with an additional innermost circle for online ego networks. In parallel to studies on generic users, there are some studies that focus on specific communities that are claimed to be using the online platforms for self-promotion and increase public appearance. In [15], the ego network structure of European politicians are analyzed to understand if they are trying to break the limitation on active relationships number while in [16] a similar analysis has been carried out for

journalists. On the other hand, in [17], the effect of ego network structure on information diffusion has been analyzed.

2.2. Multilayer Networks

The literature on multilayer networks is rapidly expanding. The reader may refer to studies [18, 7, 19] for a detailed survey on multilayer networks, and to [19, 20] for a unified mathematical models. Multilayer networks have attracted research attention from different domains such as biology, physics, and social sciences, and have been applied to a diverse range of problems, from protein interactions to information diffusion and illness spread in the social networks. Here, we will briefly discuss the studies that are closer to our work.

Multilayer network analysis generally focuses on the global properties of a network. There are numerous studies that suggest new approaches to adapt existing single-layer network metrics for the multilayer domain. In [20], the authors discuss the generalization of some network metrics such as degree centrality, clustering coefficient, and modularity in the scope of the framework and mathematical model they suggested to represent multilayer network, and in [21] for multiplex networks. In [19, 18], the authors try to create a unified terminology and network metrics for the multilayer networks. On the other hand, one of the most studied topics in multilayer networks is diffusion dynamics [22, 23, 24, 25] especially disease spread and information diffusion. Another research question gaining popularity is the correlation between the layers of multilayer networks [26, 27]. Unfortunately, the validation of the suggested models on real datasets is challenging due to the scarcity of real-world datasets that can be utilized for multilayer network studies. Therefore, in most of these studies, the main approach is using randomized networks to validate the generality and validity of the approaches.

There are studies on modeling user behaviors on cross-platforms such as [28] where the behavioral characteristics of users per platform and their cross-platform tendencies have been analyzed for multiple online social media such as *Facebook*, *Twitter*, *Instagram* and *LinkedIn*. However, there are not many studies on cognitive resource allocation within multilayer networks. All the studies that verify the existence of cognitive limitations on managing personal relationships, mentioned in Section 2.1, are modeled as a single-layer network. To the best of our knowledge, there are just a few studies that characterize the cognitive resource allocation in different communication channels. In [10], the social signatures of individuals based on ranked

ego network structure are examined in multichannel communications: phone calls and text messages. How individuals allocate their time among their relationships and the invariant of these characteristics between different channels of communication is shown. In [11], Dunbar’s ego network model based on the hierarchical structure with five intimacy level has been validated on multichannel communications (phone calls and text messages) in addition to showing that alters in the inner circles of the ego networks are generally close to the workplace or home, and usage of both calls and texting at the same time is higher for these relationships. The multichannel analyses of ego networks are based on the comparison of ego networks in different channels instead of modeling the ego networks as multilayer networks where each layer correspond to a context/community with the same communication channels.

3. The Dataset

In this work, we consider communities of users that interact with each other on Reddit. Reddit, the so-called “front page of the internet”, is a collection of forums on different topics where users can create, share, and discuss news and updates about them. Reddit consists of subreddits, also called communities. Reddit is ranked sixth in the USA, and eleventh all around the world, among the most-used social platforms². Currently, there are more than 430 million monthly active users and 2.2 million subreddits³. In this paper, we assume that each subreddit, where a user posts comments, corresponds to a layer in the multilayer ego network of that user (ego). A subreddit is considered *active* if there are at least five comments per day, and, currently, there are 130,000 active subreddits³. Reddit is not only a popular social platform but also one of the few platforms with easy access to its data and well-defined communities of interest, which makes it a popular platform to study communities and human behaviors.

We use the Pushshift API⁴ to access Reddit data [29] since the Pushshift’s API rate limits are much more flexible than the Reddit API’s⁵ ones. Pushshift contains monthly collections of all subreddits. We downloaded the subreddit

²(accessed on December 17, 2020) <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2020-global-digital-overview>

³(accessed on December 17, 2020) <https://www.oberlo.com/blog/reddit-statistics>

⁴<https://pushshift.io/>

⁵<https://www.reddit.com/dev/api/>

dump of August 2019 (one-month timeline). In the dump, there are approximately 21 million submissions, 146 million comments, 141 million subreddits, and 7 million users. Submissions are posts, subtopics, or news created by the users under a subreddit. The users can comment on submissions or another user’s comment. The dump file includes all the information about the posts and comments published during the month, in addition to the unique identifiers (IDs) of parent comments and posts. However, the author information of the parent comments and posts (parent authors) do not exist in the dump file if it is not published within the same month. Therefore, we need to download also them.

There are some comments that are deleted by the creator yet exist with missing information in the dump. After the download process of the subreddit dump file, we have removed these comments with missing information. Still, we don’t have information about the authors/users of the parent comments, as we mentioned in the previous paragraph. To construct relationships, we must have the authors’ information about the parent comments and posts. To this aim, we used Pushift API to download parent comments and posts (if they are not published within the same month of the dump file) and extract their authors’ information (name and unique id of the user). There are some parent comments and posts for which we could not access their author information. Therefore, we filtered out the comments if they have missing information or their parent authors are not accessible via API. Then, we extract the user relationships based on the parent information where authors of the comments in the dump file are the egos, and their parent authors are the alters. The set of relationships of a user consists of the parent authors of the comments that belong to the user. Figure 2 shows the distribution of the number of relationships each user maintains. As it can be seen from the figure, there are some users with a number of relationships so large that is implausible for a human user. This strongly suggests that there are some bot accounts in the dataset, which we want to discard since the focus of the work is multilayer relationships among human users (see Section 3.1). Note also that, to be able to construct multilayer ego networks, we should focus on users that have activity at least in two different subreddits with a few relationships. Therefore, we are filtering out users that don’t have activity in at least two subreddits with ten relationships. After filtering these egos, we are left with 321,995 users.

Figure 2: The distribution of relationship number per user.

3.1. Filtering Non-human Accounts

As we have seen from Figure 2, there are users with thousands of relationships for just a one-month timeline, activity too extreme for human accounts. In this section, we discuss how we have identified and discarded potential bot accounts. Specifically, we have applied a combination of manually labeled lists and keyword matching. There are different types of non-human accounts on Reddit, such as moderator bots that carry out common tasks and organize the communities⁶ or bots designed with different motivations such as propaganda of some political groups as mentioned in the Reddit’s Transparency Report 2017⁷. To identify these accounts not controlled by humans, we use three bot lists: a list of Russian bot accounts released by Reddit⁷, a list created by Reddit’s bot detector bot⁸, and a third bot list created by a Reddit user⁹. In addition to these lists, we also consider accounts as non-human if they include the keywords *bot*, *robot*, and *moderator* in their user names. In Table 1, the number of human and non-human accounts, and the percentage of non-human accounts are shown. Specifically, these numbers are reported as a function of the number of overall relationships a user has (number of relationship bin with width size 1k). The percentage of

⁶https://www.reddit.com/r/modguide/comments/ep7aza/moderator_bots_what_they_are_and_what_they_can_do/

⁷https://www.reddit.com/r/announcements/comments/8bb85p/reddits_2017_transparency_report_and_suspect/

⁸<https://www.reddit.com/r/autowikibot/wiki/redditbots>

⁹https://www.reddit.com/r/botwatch/comments/1wg6f6/bot_list_i_built_a_bot_to_find_other_bots_so_far/cf1nu8p/

non-human accounts is generally more than 50% for users with more than 3k relationships. The number of accounts that have more than 3k relationships is quite small compared to the ones with less than 3k relationships. Therefore, we filtered out these users since the effect of removing them is negligible. We have also removed the users with less than 3k relationships if they fall into the non-human account definition as mentioned above.

Table 1: Percentage of detected bots as a function of the total number of relationships of users.

relationship number	human	non-human	bot percentage (%)
(0, 1k]	320,063	1,019	0.32
(1k, 2k]	785	27	3.33
(2k, 3k]	46	8	14.81
(3k, 4k]	5	6	54.55
(4k, 5k]	6	5	45.45
(5k, 6k]	1	1	50.00
(6k, 7k]	3	2	40.00
(7k, 8k]	3	2	40.00
(9k, 10k]	0	4	100
(10k, 11k]	1	0	0.00
(11k, 12k]	1	1	50.00
(12k, 13k]	0	1	100
(13k, 14k]	0	1	100
(16k, 17k]	1	0	0.00
(18k, 19k]	0	1	100

4. The Ego Network Model

As discussed in Sections 1 and 2, the Dunbar’s ego network model is a hierarchical organization of the relationships of an individual. This hierarchy is based on the intimacy levels between the individual (ego) and its peer (alter) engaged in the relationship. In the literature, the closeness/intimacy between an ego and its alters is generally represented by means of the contact frequency [2, 4, 5, 30, 31]. As shown in Figure 1, an ego network consists of inclusive circles with typical sizes around 1.5, 5, 15, 45, 150, respectively. The intimacy decreases when moving from inner circles (higher contact frequency) to outer ones. The outermost circle represents the ego network size (~ 150 alters [1], also known as Dunbar’s number). The relationships beyond the fifth circle are not included in the ego network construction process since they

are not *active*, i.e., the egos do not use their cognitive resources regularly to engage with these people.

4.1. Construction of Single-layer Ego Networks

In this section, we briefly summarise how single-layer ego networks are constructed in the related literature. Single-layer ego networks provide a benchmark against which our novel results on multilayer ego networks are compared. The single-layer ego networks for our dataset will be analyzed in Section 5. Note that here we are constructing single-layer ego networks starting from a multilayer graph. This boils down to flattening the layer information, such that the layer where interactions take place is not important anymore. The first step in computing single-layer ego networks is to calculate the ego-alter contact frequency. The contact frequency for online relationships is calculated as the number of direct interactions divided by the length of the relationships in years. In the Reddit dataset, direct communication occurs via comments where a user replies to another user’s post or comment. Since a user can comment multiple times on another user’s posts and comments on different subreddits, we can adopt the contact frequency formula commonly used in the literature between an ego i and alter j as:

$$w_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{l=1}^L N_l^{(i,j)}}{T_R^{(i,j)}}, \quad (1)$$

where w_{ij} is contact frequency (intimacy), L is the number of subreddits (layers) that ego i commented on the posts of alter j , $N_l^{(i,j)}$ is the number of comments of ego i on posts of alter j in the subreddit(layer) l , and $T_R^{(i,j)}$ is the time length of the relationship starting from the first comment between i, j among all subreddits and ending with the download time of the dataset.

After calculating the intimacy of the relationships as mentioned in the previous paragraph, we can group the relationships into intimacy levels. To this aim, and similarly to [16, 11, 32], we use the Mean Shift algorithm [33]. The advantage of Mean Shift, against, e.g., more traditional clustering methods like k -means, is that it automatically selects the optimal number of clusters. Each of the clusters found by Mean Shift corresponds to a *ring* \mathcal{R} in the ego network (Figure 1), with \mathcal{R}_1 being the one with the highest average contact frequency (i.e., intimacy). Then, circles \mathcal{C} are obtained as the union set of concentric rings. Thus, it holds that $\mathcal{C}_i = \mathcal{C}_{i-1} \cup \mathcal{R}_i$, with initial condition $\mathcal{C}_1 = \mathcal{R}_1$.

4.2. Multilayer Ego Network Model

Now, we focus on how the egos maintain their relationships in different contexts/layers based on the different communities they are a member of. Each subreddit in our dataset represents a different community, where members share the same interest and use the platform to create content about these interests and share and discuss them. In multilayer ego network analysis, we focus on the subreddits the ego is a member of, and we create layers of the multilayer network based on these communities. Each layer of the multilayer ego network corresponds to a subreddit (community/context) that the ego has activity on. Figure 3 shows the Dunbar’s ego network model on a multilayer structure where the ego interacts in l layers. There may be alters that are common among different layers that create inter-layer dependencies.

Figure 3: Dunbar’s ego network model in a multilayer setting.

To create multilayer ego networks, we compartmentalise interactions within the subreddit where they happen. Hence, we construct one intra-layer ego network per subreddit. Since each subreddit is a layer in the multilayer ego network, an alter may exist in different layers of the network if the ego interacts with it in different subreddits. When the context of the interaction changes, the intimacy level of the relationship may also change. Accordingly, in which circle the alter is located may change from layer to layer. Therefore,

a contact frequency between an ego i and alter j is calculated for each layer l as:

$$w_{(ij,l)} = \frac{N_l^{(i,j)}}{T_{R_l}^{(i,j)}}, \quad (2)$$

where $w_{(ij,l)}$ is contact frequency (intimacy) on layer l , $N_l^{(i,j)}$ is number of comments of ego i on posts of alter j on layer l , and $T_{R_l}^{(i,j)}$ is the length of the relationships between i and j starting from the first comment on layer l and ending with the download time of the dataset. After obtaining the intimacy of relationships ($w_{ij,l}$), we use the Mean Shift algorithm (described in Section 4.1) per layer to group relationships based on their contact frequencies.

After creating an ego network for each layer, we are able to analyze the cognitive resource distribution among the circles in each layer. We may infer how much of the total capacity is allocated per layer and how this allocated capacity is organized through circles within layers. However, we still need to have a general picture of allocated resources per circle independent of the layers to understand the total capacity of the egos per circle. We define the total capacity of an ego i for a circle x as the summation of *intra-layer circle sizes*:

$$C_x = \sum_{l=1}^L C_{(x,l)} \quad (3)$$

where C_x is *inter-layer circle size*, L is the number of layers of the ego i , $C_{(x,l)}$ is the x^{th} circle size of ego i in layer l .

5. The Analysis of Single-layer Ego Networks

In this section, we study the single-layer ego network of our Reddit users. This gives us the opportunity to compare Reddit users' ego networks to those analyzed for other social networks both in the online and offline world. We construct the ego networks as discussed in Section 4.1. The distribution of the optimal circle numbers is shown in Figure 4. As we can see from the figure, the distribution concentrates between 2 and 5, with mode value 3. In the related literature, the average number of circles has been shown to be typically around 4 [6] in offline and 4-5 in online social networks [5]. The distribution in Figure 4 shows that the circle numbers are compatible with these previous findings.

Figure 4: Distribution of the optimal circle number.

The circles of ego networks represent the intimacy levels of the relationships. Having a different optimal number of circles implies that there are different patterns in allocating cognitive resources. Therefore, before calculating the average number of alters, we group egos based on their optimal circle number. In Table 2, we show the average number of alters per circle after this grouping. As we can see from the table, the size of the outermost circle (which, conventionally corresponds to the ego network size), shown in the last non-empty cell of each row, increases for the egos with a higher optimal number of circles. Thus, the egos who have more relationships tend to create more intimacy levels among their alters. For the egos with 4 and 5 circles, the average ego network sizes are 123 and 153 which are quite close to Dunbar’s number. In general, the circle sizes are slightly smaller than those observed in the related literature for online social networks [34]. One possible explanation lies in the fact that we do not force all egos to feature 4 or 5 circles as it is often the case in the related literature. By combining, e.g., circle C2 for all egos in Table 2, we would indeed get an average value that is higher than most of the sizes observed for the optimal circle number groups. However, our approach allows to better preserve the true structure of ego networks.

6. The Analysis of Multilayer Ego Networks

In this section, we present the results on multilayer ego networks that are constructed as explained in Section 4.2. Here, we discard egos that engage with only one subreddit, since they do not provide multiple layers to study in

Table 2: Circle sizes (average \pm confidence interval) in the single-layer setting.

opt. circle number	# egos	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	49,282	4.16 \pm 0.027	74.96 \pm 0.411			
3	83,682	1.75 \pm 0.008	8.66 \pm 0.038	97.42 \pm 0.448		
4	71,388	1.33 \pm 0.005	3.96 \pm 0.017	14.34 \pm 0.066	123.41 \pm 0.648	
5	46,636	1.19 \pm 0.005	2.96 \pm 0.013	6.83 \pm 0.034	21.39 \pm 0.123	153.97 \pm 1.063

our analysis. In Figure 5, we show the distribution of the number of subreddits each ego is active on. There are some users with a very large number of subreddits (> 300). These extreme values may, however, correspond to egos who invest a negligible amount of their cognitive resources to each of their subreddits. Negligible efforts are outliers for our analysis, since ego network structures, by definition, emerge when the ego has to distribute a significant cognitive effort across its alters. Therefore, we decided to remove, for each ego, all the subreddits where they do not allocate at least 10% of their cognitive resources. This cognitive effort is measured in terms of number of comments on the subreddit. Specifically, we use the following formula:

$$AR_l = \frac{N_l}{\sum_{k=1}^L N_k} \times 100, \quad (4)$$

where AR_l is the percentage of allocated resource for subreddit l , N_l the number of comment in subreddit l , and L is the number of subreddits. As an example, let’s say we have a user *Author1* who commented in 10 different subreddits as shown in Table 3. This user’s allocated resources for the subreddit *AskReddit* is the percentage of comments in *AskReddit* with respect to all the comments of the user in all subreddits. After we calculate the allocated resources for each subreddit of the user, we rank the subreddits based on this cognitive effort. If there is a tie between two subreddits, we randomly assign the rank since the allocated resources are the same. Note that this ranking is performed on an ego-by-ego basis. Removing the users’ subreddits based on the allocated resources reduces the number of subreddits per user drastically, as shown in Figure 6. This indicates that users focus their attention on a just few communities (in all cases, less than eight) even though they are part of many more. Note that there are also some egos that allocate all their “significant” cognitive effort to just one subreddit. These egos will be removed because they are not useful for our analysis.

Figure 5: Distribution of subreddit number per ego.

Table 3: An example of one particular user’s cognitive resource allocation per subreddit.

author	subreddit	comment #	comment %	subreddit rank
Author1	AskReddit	13	22.41	1
	Brawlstars	11	18.96	2
	shittybrawlstars	11	18.96	3
	sbuby	5	8.62	4
	gaming	5	8.62	5
	youngpeopleyoutube	3	5.17	6
	apexlegends	3	5.17	7
	softwaregore	3	5.17	8
	wholesomememes	2	3.44	9
	4PanelCringe	2	3.44	10

6.1. The subreddit perspective

In this section, we set out to investigate how the intra-layer ego network structures change when the cognitive efforts associated with the corresponding subreddit decrease. Imagine several multilayer ego networks (like the one in Figure 3), sorted by the cognitive resources allocated to each layer, and stacked side-by-side. In this section, we study together the ego networks belonging to the first, second, ..., n -th row. Even though the filtering discussed in the previous section has significantly reduced the heterogeneity of egos in terms of the number of subreddits they meaningfully engage with, Figure 6 shows that there are still some differences between egos. In this section, we analyze together egos whose cognitive efforts are spread across the same number of subreddits in order to make the comparison fairer. As it can be seen from Figure 6, most of the egos have two or three subreddits (note that the number of egos is in *log* scale). The number of egos with more than five subreddits is less than three hundred samples over a total of more

Figure 6: Distribution of the number of subreddits per ego after removing subreddits with less than 10% cognitive resource allocation.

than 250K. Therefore, in the following, we will focus on egos whose subreddit number is between two and five, cases for which we have a significant number of samples, at least a hundred egos per subreddit on average.

Even if we group together egos with the same number of “meaningful” subreddits, egos are still heterogeneous in terms of the optimal number of social circles that their intra-layer ego networks exhibit on each subreddit. In order to ensure a fair comparison from this standpoint as well, we will group together egos with the same number of optimal social circles. Summarising, in the following, we will consider separately users with the same number (say s) of meaningful subreddits. Then, when studying their subreddit ranked n -th, we will separately analyze users that have $2, \dots, 5$ circles in their layer n -th’s ego network. We denote synthetically each group as (s, n, τ) -class where s denotes the number of subreddits, n denotes the rank of the subreddits, and τ denotes optimal circle number. Note that, since egos may have a different optimal number of circles on each intra-layer ego network, the set of nodes in class (s, n, τ) and those $(s, n + 1, \tau)$ are generally different. For example, let’s say we have an ego with four circles in the first subreddit and five circles in the second subreddit, as shown in Figure 7 with *EGO 2*. When we study the first and second subreddits grouping by $\tau = 4$ (shown with green rectangles in the figure), this ego will be included in the first subreddit group while not included in the second subreddit group.

Figure 8 shows the distribution of the optimal circle number (as obtained via Mean Shift, see Section 4) for egos with the same number of subreddits. Each colored bar shows a ranked subreddit. Thus, each figure fully describes the class (s, n, τ) for a fixed s . For example, in Figure 8a, the egos that

Figure 7: Dunbar’s ego network model in a multilayer setting.

are active in two subreddits ($s = 2$) are visualized. Gray bars show the distribution of the circle number τ for the subreddits that are ranked as the most significant for their egos, while yellow bars represent the same distribution but for the second most active subreddit. Let us compare the distributions with different colors within each plot. For example, if we look at Figure 8a, we see that the distribution of τ in the most and least significant subreddits are very similar. The same similarity also exists in the other plots for egos with a different number of significant subreddits. We can infer that the distribution of the optimal number of circles τ is very consistent regardless of whether we focus on the most popular or the least popular subreddits. In addition, the similarity between the distributions also persists for the egos with different numbers of subreddits. Thus, we can infer that, regardless of how many layers there are, the optimal circle number is mainly located between 2 and 5.

We can now study the intra-layer ego networks for each class (s, n, τ) . In Table 4, we show the circle sizes for egos with two significant subreddits (i.e., $s = 2$). The results for egos with 3 to 5 subreddits can be seen in Appendix A. Each color in Table 4 shows the grouping of egos based on their optimal number of circles. When we compare the ego network size in the first and second subreddits of egos with the same optimal number of circles (color-wise comparison in the table), we can see that the outermost circles (which corresponds to the whole ego network size) in the first subreddit (the one taking

Figure 8: Distribution of the optimal number of circles for egos with different number of “significant” subreddits.

up the majority of cognitive resources) are always larger than outermost circles in the second subreddit. The results in Appendix A also show that the sizes of outermost circles decrease as the number of “significant” subreddits for the ego grows. Thus, the outermost circles are strongly dependent on the multilayer structure: egos redistribute their cognitive efforts depending on the total number of their significant subreddits and their individual rankings. Vice versa, the inner circles are of very similar size, regardless of the subreddit ranking. And this is confirmed also for egos with a different number s of important subreddits (Appendix A). This suggests that, independently of how many cognitive resources we allocate for the subreddit itself, there is a limitation on how many alters we can have in the most intimate circles. This finding is consistent with observations from the related literature: the relationships in the innermost circles require significant cognitive efforts for their nurturing, hence they cannot be increased at will [35].

Table 4: Intra-layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with 2 significant subreddits.

optimal circle number	subreddit rank	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	1	2.52 \pm 0.019	32.57 \pm 0.227			
	2	1.92 \pm 0.011	19.81 \pm 0.105			
3	1	1.44 \pm 0.009	5.6 \pm 0.038	43.33 \pm 0.349		
	2	1.28 \pm 0.007	4.17 \pm 0.027	26.49 \pm 0.214		
4	1	1.23 \pm 0.007	3.29 \pm 0.022	9.7 \pm 0.078	57.48 \pm 0.612	
	2	1.17 \pm 0.008	2.87 \pm 0.022	7.29 \pm 0.073	36.68 \pm 0.492	
5	1	1.16 \pm 0.008	2.74 \pm 0.02	5.77 \pm 0.051	15.28 \pm 0.169	76.92 \pm 1.112
	2	1.12 \pm 0.01	2.55 \pm 0.026	4.95 \pm 0.061	11.58 \pm 0.186	51.18 \pm 1.117

6.1.1. Take-home messages

In this section, we investigated how the intra-layer ego network structure changes when the cognitive efforts associated with the corresponding subreddit decrease. Our main findings are the followings:

- The distribution of the optimal number of circles τ is very stable, regardless of the subreddit ranking or of the number of “significant” subreddits for the ego. In addition, the body of the distribution is concentrated between 2 and 5 social circles. We refer to this property as **self-similarity of multilayer ego networks**.
- Independently of the subreddit ranking (i.e., of how many cognitive resources we allocate to it), there is a limitation on how many alters we can have in the most intimate circles. This confirms, in the multilayer domain, a phenomenon observed in single-layer ego networks: **the innermost circle is small and its size has little variability**, because expanding this circle requires significant cognitive efforts which do not pay off for the ego.
- Vice versa, the outermost circle tends to grow with the ranking of the subreddit, i.e., with the cognitive efforts allocated to the layer. Its size also decreases as the number of “significant” subreddits for the ego grows. This implies that the cognitive effort allocated to each subreddit is substantially reorganized depending on the multilayer structure.
- Taking together the two previous points, we can speculate that **egos**

accommodate multiple layers by adapting the outermost layers without significantly affecting the innermost ones.

In the next section, we further investigate the latter point, by considering how ego networks vary, for the same ego, across its different layers.

6.2. The ego perspective

In this section, we zoom in on egos that have the same optimal circle number τ across all layers (i.e., subreddits). While in the previous section our focus was on subreddits with different cognitive involvement, we now direct our attention to individual egos. Specifically, we want to follow egos across the multiple communities they engage with and observe how their ego networks change. Referring again to Figure 3, this is equivalent to scanning vertically individual multilayer ego networks. To ensure a more direct comparison, we analyze together egos that have the same optimal circle number τ across all subreddits. To clarify this point, please consider Figure 9, which applies to egos with only two significant subreddits (i.e., $s = 2$). We tally the number of egos with a target τ in each subreddit. In the previous section, we analyzed together egos on the same row (column) for the top(bottom)-ranked subreddit. Now, we focus on the diagonal combinations. With this approach, it is easy to assess whether circles shrink or expand across layers, without having to factor in whether their overall number changes as well. While Figure 9 only captures egos with two significant subreddits, in Figure 10 we focus on the diagonal egos for any significant subreddit number. The number of egos with the same optimal circle number in all layers decreases drastically (y-axis is in log scale) as the number of significant subreddits of the ego increases. In the following, as we did in the previous section, we will focus on the optimal circle number in $[2, 5]$, since that is where there are enough samples to reliably characterize the average circle sizes at the different layers.

For the sake of clarity, let us focus our discussion on the egos with two significant subreddits. The results of circle sizes for the egos with three subreddits are provided in Appendix B and they substantially confirm the findings that we illustrate below (for a higher number of subreddits, the number of samples for the different optimal number of circles is too low to draw reliable conclusions). Table 5 shows the circle sizes of egos with two subreddits and the same optimal circle number in both of them. Basically, Table 5 is a restricted version of Table 4 where the egos that do not belong to the diagonal of Figure 9 are dropped. The two tables showcase similar

Figure 9: Heatmap with tally of egos with each combination of optimal circles number between the two significant subreddits. A cell in position i, j reports the tally of the number of egos with i circles on the first subreddit and j circles on the second one.

Figure 10: Histogram of the optimal circle number as the number of significant subreddits varies.

patterns. Specifically, the innermost circle is pretty much unaffected by the subreddit ranking, while the outermost one changes significantly. This further confirms the findings from Table 4: the stability of the innermost layer and the variability of the outermost ones are not a by-product of analyzing together egos with a different optimal number of circles at different layers. Indeed, when controlling for the latter, the results do not change.

Let us now consider more in detail the outermost circle. By definition (Section 4), its size corresponds to the ego network size, so the two terms will be used interchangeably. In the following, we want to investigate what is the relationship between the ego network size across the ranked subreddits. Specifically, if an ego features a large ego network on the top-ranked subred-

Table 5: Intra layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with the same optimal circle number in both subreddits.

circle number	subreddit rank	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	1	2.5 ± 0.026	32.09 ± 0.312			
	2	1.68 ± 0.015	17.63 ± 0.138			
3	1	1.53 ± 0.018	6.18 ± 0.077	47.34 ± 0.712		
	2	1.23 ± 0.01	3.84 ± 0.04	24.07 ± 0.32		
4	1	1.31 ± 0.022	3.75 ± 0.068	11.53 ± 0.23	67.96 ± 1.774	
	2	1.16 ± 0.014	2.79 ± 0.037	6.97 ± 0.125	34.42 ± 0.845	
5	1	1.25 ± 0.036	3.13 ± 0.09	7.04 ± 0.222	19.35 ± 0.691	97.5 ± 4.438
	2	1.12 ± 0.022	2.50 ± 0.051	4.83 ± 0.12	11.34 ± 0.357	48.48 ± 2.035

dit, will it also present a large ego network on the bottom-ranked subreddit, or will it compensate its efforts by shrinking the ego network on the bottom-ranked one? In order to address these questions, in Figure 11 we show a scatterplot of the ego network sizes in the top vs. bottom subreddit (again, we group together egos with the same optimal number of circles). The lines represent the linear regression that fits best the data. The plots show a clear correlation between the ego network sizes: an ego that has more alters in the first subreddit tends to have more alters also in the second subreddit. This suggests that egos distribute their cognitive efforts proportionally across their layers instead of assigning a fixed effort to the top-ranked subreddit and allocating whatever is left to the other subreddits. We now carry out the same correlation analysis for all the social circles, not just the outermost one. In order to observe a significant dynamic in terms of circles, we focus on egos with five as optimal circle number. We show the corresponding scatterplot with best-fit regression lines in Figure 12 (the plots for different optimal circle numbers are shown in Appendix C). We observe that the correlation between the circle sizes is much smaller in the inner circles (almost nonexistent) with respect to the outer circles, and it grows moving outwards. This confirms, once again, the very different nature of innermost and outermost circles, with the former varying very little and taking up a fixed cognitive effort while the latter are more dynamic and rearranged across the different subreddits.

As already discussed, the positive correlation at the outermost circles suggests that egos allocate their global cognitive efforts to subreddits in a way that is proportional to their ranking. We now investigate whether these efforts, when considered together, are characterized by any specific pattern. To this aim, we consider the inter-layer circle size as the sum of the size of the

Figure 11: Ego network sizes in subreddit 1 vs subreddit 2, for egos with optimal circle number between 2 and 5.

intra-layer circles, as described in Section 4.2. We refer to this cumulative quantity as the total cognitive capacity that the ego allocates to that circle. We plot the size of inter-layer circles in Figure 13 (Appendix D includes inter-layer circles for different optimal circle numbers). As we can see, the distributions tend to concentrate around a specific value, with the mean and median being close to each other. Figure 13 shows that the organization of inter-layer social circles mirrors that of intra-layer ones and single-layer social circles, further confirming the self-similarity of ego networks across different scales.

6.2.1. Take-home messages

In this section, we investigated how the ego network structure changes across layers when we focus on homogeneous sets of egos that have the same optimal circle number in all layers. Our main findings are the followings:

Figure 12: Circle sizes in subreddit 1 vs subreddit 2 for egos that have 5 circles on both subreddits.

- Egos distribute their cognitive efforts proportionally across their layers instead of assigning a fixed effort to the top-ranked subreddit and allocating whatever is left to the other subreddits.
- Even when tracking individual egos and not individual subreddits (as in Section 6.1), the innermost circles vary very little and take up a fixed cognitive effort, while the outermost circles are more dynamic and are rearranged across the different subreddits.
- Inter-layer social circles mirror intra-layer and single-layer ones, and this further confirms the self-similarity of ego networks across different scales.

7. Conclusion

In this work, we have studied how humans allocate their cognitive resources to social relationships that happen on a multilayer graph. To this

Figure 13: Inter-layer circle size for egos with 2 significant subreddits and with 5 circles on both subreddits.

aim, we have adapted the well-known ego network model from the anthropology literature in order to capture multilayer interactions. The dataset we use for our investigation is a month-long Reddit dump, where each subreddit is treated as a different layer. We found that multilayer ego networks are self-similar: their structural properties are very stable, regardless of the number of “significant” subreddits (i.e., those taking up considerable cognitive efforts) for the ego or their ranking, and concentrated between 2 and 5 social circles that is quite similar to the general ego network model. We also discovered that egos distribute their cognitive efforts proportionally across their layers instead of assigning a fixed effort to the top-ranked subreddit and allocating whatever is left to the other subreddits. Finally, we have observed that egos accommodate multiple layers by adapting the outermost circles without significantly affecting the innermost ones. Indeed, the innermost circle is small and its size has little variability. Vice versa, the outermost circle tends to grow with the ranking of the subreddit, i.e., with the cognitive efforts allocated to the layer. However, its size also decreases as the number of “significant” subreddits for the ego grows.

Appendix A. The subreddit perspective - intra-layer circle sizes

Table A.6: Intra-layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with 2 significant subreddits.

opt. circle number	# egos	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	1	2.52 \pm 0.019	32.57 \pm 0.227			
	2	1.92 \pm 0.011	19.81 \pm 0.105			
3	1	1.44 \pm 0.009	5.6 \pm 0.038	43.33 \pm 0.349		
	2	1.28 \pm 0.007	4.17 \pm 0.027	26.49 \pm 0.214		
4	1	1.23 \pm 0.007	3.29 \pm 0.022	9.7 \pm 0.078	57.48 \pm 0.612	
	2	1.17 \pm 0.008	2.87 \pm 0.022	7.29 \pm 0.073	36.68 \pm 0.492	
5	1	1.16 \pm 0.008	2.74 \pm 0.02	5.77 \pm 0.051	15.28 \pm 0.169	76.92 \pm 1.112
	2	1.12 \pm 0.01	2.55 \pm 0.026	4.95 \pm 0.061	11.58 \pm 0.186	51.18 \pm 1.117

Table A.7: Intra-layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with 3 significant subreddits.

opt. circle number	# egos	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	1	2.29 \pm 0.018	27.1 \pm 0.194			
	2	1.89 \pm 0.013	19.0 \pm 0.119			
	3	1.65 \pm 0.01	13.99 \pm 0.099			
3	1	1.37 \pm 0.009	4.92 \pm 0.037	34.79 \pm 0.33		
	2	1.27 \pm 0.008	4.02 \pm 0.031	24.62 \pm 0.247		
	3	1.21 \pm 0.008	3.52 \pm 0.029	18.97 \pm 0.225		
4	1	1.19 \pm 0.008	3.06 \pm 0.025	8.38 \pm 0.087	45.73 \pm 0.612	
	2	1.16 \pm 0.009	2.83 \pm 0.027	6.99 \pm 0.089	34.43 \pm 0.609	
	3	1.13 \pm 0.011	2.69 \pm 0.029	6.22 \pm 0.095	28.21 \pm 0.627	
5	1	1.14 \pm 0.01	2.65 \pm 0.027	5.3 \pm 0.066	13.02 \pm 0.203	61.66 \pm 1.218
	2	1.11 \pm 0.013	2.53 \pm 0.032	4.86 \pm 0.076	11.16 \pm 0.23	49.32 \pm 1.394
	3	1.11 \pm 0.017	2.47 \pm 0.039	4.67 \pm 0.093	10.32 \pm 0.289	42.33 \pm 1.556

Table A.8: Intra-layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with 4 significant subreddits.

opt. circle number	# egos	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	1	2.17 \pm 0.03	23.95 \pm 0.304			
	2	1.85 \pm 0.022	18.13 \pm 0.2			
	3	1.69 \pm 0.019	14.29 \pm 0.18			
	4	1.58 \pm 0.017	12.15 \pm 0.154			
3	1	1.33 \pm 0.015	4.54 \pm 0.059	30.18 \pm 0.503		
	2	1.26 \pm 0.014	3.9 \pm 0.054	23.14 \pm 0.429		
	3	1.21 \pm 0.013	3.5 \pm 0.05	18.75 \pm 0.375		
	4	1.2 \pm 0.015	3.33 \pm 0.052	16.85 \pm 0.397		
4	1	1.18 \pm 0.015	2.95 \pm 0.044	7.6 \pm 0.145	39.01 \pm 0.958	
	2	1.15 \pm 0.016	2.76 \pm 0.045	6.68 \pm 0.152	31.44 \pm 0.973	
	3	1.13 \pm 0.018	2.69 \pm 0.054	6.22 \pm 0.168	28.06 \pm 1.108	
	4	1.13 \pm 0.022	2.64 \pm 0.056	5.89 \pm 0.18	25.57 \pm 1.109	
5	1	1.13 \pm 0.02	2.59 \pm 0.048	5.07 \pm 0.122	12.26 \pm 0.389	55.13 \pm 2.237
	2	1.11 \pm 0.028	2.53 \pm 0.067	4.76 \pm 0.146	10.7 \pm 0.442	44.02 \pm 2.599
	3	1.1 \pm 0.029	2.49 \pm 0.08	4.68 \pm 0.174	9.8 \pm 0.448	39.69 \pm 2.567
	4	1.12 \pm 0.036	2.42 \pm 0.075	4.29 \pm 0.162	9.44 \pm 0.522	37.53 \pm 2.996

Table A.9: Intra-layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with 5 significant subreddits.

opt. circle number	# egos	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
1	1	2.04 \pm 0.069	21.45 \pm 0.557			
	2	1.8 \pm 0.053	16.87 \pm 0.455			
	3	1.68 \pm 0.047	14.23 \pm 0.409			
	4	1.57 \pm 0.045	12.57 \pm 0.401			
	5	1.51 \pm 0.039	11.34 \pm 0.348			
3	1	1.28 \pm 0.038	4.25 \pm 0.152	26.36 \pm 1.137		
	2	1.23 \pm 0.034	3.67 \pm 0.123	21.17 \pm 0.963		
	3	1.22 \pm 0.035	3.48 \pm 0.127	17.85 \pm 0.97		
	4	1.19 \pm 0.037	3.39 \pm 0.135	16.67 \pm 0.965		
	5	1.18 \pm 0.036	3.21 \pm 0.124	15.25 \pm 0.877		
4	1	1.15 \pm 0.035	2.81 \pm 0.115	6.85 \pm 0.413	32.13 \pm 2.334	
	2	1.17 \pm 0.046	2.82 \pm 0.134	6.79 \pm 0.42	29.91 \pm 2.434	
	3	1.1 \pm 0.043	2.59 \pm 0.122	5.92 \pm 0.417	24.69 \pm 2.658	
	4	1.12 \pm 0.052	2.61 \pm 0.131	5.73 \pm 0.419	23.93 \pm 2.816	
	5	1.11 \pm 0.05	2.56 \pm 0.142	5.71 \pm 0.402	21.61 \pm 2.592	
5	1	1.08 \pm 0.044	2.43 \pm 0.121	4.67 \pm 0.284	10.57 \pm 0.886	46.37 \pm 5.488
	2	1.06 \pm 0.044	2.51 \pm 0.17	4.92 \pm 0.433	11.01 \pm 1.314	43.44 \pm 6.941
	3	1.13 \pm 0.081	2.38 \pm 0.158	4.37 \pm 0.39	9.51 \pm 1.236	39.68 \pm 6.328
	4	1.1 \pm 0.1	2.44 \pm 0.243	4.27 \pm 0.489	8.73 \pm 1.304	32.67 \pm 6.649
	5	1.14 \pm 0.144	2.47 \pm 0.216	4.51 \pm 0.628	8.21 \pm 1.272	30.09 \pm 4.773

Appendix B. The ego perspective - intra layer circle sizes

Table B.10: Intra layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with the same optimal circle number in both subreddits.

circle number	subreddit rank	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	1	2.5 ± 0.026	32.09 ± 0.312			
	2	1.68 ± 0.015	17.63 ± 0.138			
3	1	1.53 ± 0.018	6.18 ± 0.077	47.34 ± 0.712		
	2	1.23 ± 0.01	3.84 ± 0.04	24.07 ± 0.32		
4	1	1.31 ± 0.022	3.75 ± 0.068	11.53 ± 0.23	67.96 ± 1.774	
	2	1.16 ± 0.014	2.79 ± 0.037	6.97 ± 0.125	34.42 ± 0.845	
5	1	1.25 ± 0.036	3.13 ± 0.09	7.04 ± 0.222	19.35 ± 0.691	97.5 ± 4.438
	2	1.12 ± 0.022	2.50 ± 0.051	4.83 ± 0.12	11.34 ± 0.357	48.48 ± 2.035

Table B.11: Intra layer circle sizes (average \pm confidence intervals) for egos with the same optimal circle number in all 3 subreddits.

circle number	subreddit rank	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5
2	1	2.33 ± 0.036	27.54 ± 0.383			
	2	1.72 ± 0.024	17.53 ± 0.22			
	3	1.43 ± 0.017	11.69 ± 0.164			
3	1	1.52 ± 0.037	5.97 ± 0.147	41.76 ± 1.257		
	2	1.28 ± 0.025	4.21 ± 0.094	26.13 ± 0.739		
	3	1.18 ± 0.02	3.34 ± 0.066	17.4 ± 0.521		
4	1	1.34 ± 0.071	3.87 ± 0.197	11.72 ± 0.639	64.49 ± 4.491	
	2	1.23 ± 0.048	3.04 ± 0.119	8.05 ± 0.416	40.13 ± 2.651	
	3	1.15 ± 0.04	2.62 ± 0.088	5.98 ± 0.287	27.52 ± 1.954	
5	1	1.3 ± 0.152	3.51 ± 0.344	7.58 ± 0.914	20.24 ± 2.331	101.11 ± 13.424
	2	1.19 ± 0.091	2.72 ± 0.235	5.78 ± 0.488	13.61 ± 1.321	63.0 ± 8.805
	3	1.08 ± 0.064	2.41 ± 0.158	4.58 ± 0.395	10.57 ± 1.262	43.24 ± 7.821

Appendix C. The ego perspective - circle sizes in subreddit 1 vs subreddit 2

Figure C.14: Circle sizes in subreddit 1 vs subreddit 2 for egos that have 2 circles on both subreddits.

Figure C.15: Circle sizes in subreddit 1 vs subreddit 2 for egos that have 3 circles on both subreddits.

Figure C.16: CCircle sizes in subreddit 1 vs subreddit 2 for egos that have 4 circles on both subreddits.

Figure C.17: Circle sizes in subreddit 1 vs subreddit 2 for egos that have 5 circles on both subreddits.

Appendix D. The ego perspective - inter-layer circle sizes

Figure D.18: Inter-layer circle size for egos with 2 significant subreddits and with 2 circles on both subreddits.

Figure D.19: Inter-layer circle size for egos with 2 significant subreddits and with 3 circles on both subreddits.

Figure D.20: Inter-layer circle size for egos with 4 significant subreddits and with 5 circles on both subreddits.

Figure D.21: Inter-layer circle size for egos with 2 significant subreddits and with 5 circles on both subreddits.

References

- [1] R. Dunbar, The social brain hypothesis, *Evolutionary Anthropology* 9 (10) (1998) 178–190.
- [2] R. A. Hill, R. I. Dunbar, Social network size in humans, *Human nature* 14 (1) (2003) 53–72.
- [3] G. Miritello, R. Lara, M. Cebrian, E. Moro, Limited communication capacity unveils strategies for human interaction, *Scientific reports* 3 (1) (2013) 1–7.
- [4] G. Miritello, E. Moro, R. Lara, R. Martínez-López, J. Belchamber, S. G. Roberts, R. I. Dunbar, Time as a limited resource: Communication strategy in mobile phone networks, *Social Networks* 35 (1) (2013) 89–95.
- [5] R. Dunbar, V. Arnaboldi, M. Conti, A. Passarella, The structure of online social networks mirrors those in the offline world, *Social Networks* 43 (2015) 39–47.
- [6] W.-X. Zhou, D. Sornette, R. a. Hill, R. I. M. Dunbar, Discrete hierarchical organization of social group sizes., *Proceedings. Biological sciences / The Royal Society* 272 (1561) (2005) 439–444.
- [7] A. Lomi, G. Robins, M. Tranmer, Introduction to multilevel social networks, *Social Networks* 100 (44) (2016) 266–268.
- [8] P. Craven, B. Wellman, The network city, *Sociological inquiry* 43 (3-4) (1973) 57–88.
- [9] M. E. Dickison, M. Magnani, L. Rossi, *Multilayer social networks*, Cambridge University Press, 2016.
- [10] S. Heydari, S. G. Roberts, R. I. Dunbar, J. Saramäki, Multichannel social signatures and persistent features of ego networks, *Applied network science* 3 (1) (2018) 8.
- [11] C. Quadri, M. Zignani, S. Gaito, G. P. Rossi, Feature-rich ego-network circles in mobile phone graphs: tie multiplexity and the role of alters, in: *2018 IEEE/ACM International Conference on Advances in Social Networks Analysis and Mining (ASONAM)*, IEEE, 2018, pp. 1280–1285.

- [12] S. Hayat, A. Rextin, A. Idris, M. Nasim, Text and phone calls: user behaviour and dual-channel communication prediction, *Human-centric Computing and Information Sciences* 10 (2020) 1–18.
- [13] S. G. Roberts, R. I. Dunbar, T. V. Pollet, T. Kuppens, Exploring variation in active network size: Constraints and ego characteristics, *Social Networks* 31 (2) (2009) 138–146.
- [14] B. Gonçalves, N. Perra, A. Vespignani, Modeling users’ activity on twitter networks: Validation of dunbar’s number, *PloS one* 6 (8) (2011) e22656.
- [15] V. Arnaboldi, A. Passarella, M. Conti, R. Dunbar, Structure of Ego-Alter Relationships of Politicians in Twitter, *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication* 22 (5) (2017) 231–247.
- [16] C. Boldrini, M. Toprak, M. Conti, A. Passarella, Twitter and the press: an ego-centred analysis, in: *Companion Proceedings of the The Web Conference 2018*, 2018, pp. 1471–1478.
- [17] V. Arnaboldi, M. Conti, A. Passarella, R. I. Dunbar, Online social networks and information diffusion: The role of ego networks, *Online Social Networks and Media* 1 (2017) 44–55.
- [18] S. Boccaletti, G. Bianconi, R. Criado, C. I. Del Genio, J. Gómez-Gardenes, M. Romance, I. Sendina-Nadal, Z. Wang, M. Zanin, The structure and dynamics of multilayer networks, *Physics Reports* 544 (1) (2014) 1–122.
- [19] M. Kivelä, A. Arenas, M. Barthelemy, J. P. Gleeson, Y. Moreno, M. A. Porter, Multilayer networks, *Journal of complex networks* 2 (3) (2014) 203–271.
- [20] M. De Domenico, A. Solé-Ribalta, E. Cozzo, M. Kivelä, Y. Moreno, M. A. Porter, S. Gómez, A. Arenas, Mathematical formulation of multilayer networks, *Physical Review X* 3 (4) (2013) 041022.
- [21] F. Battiston, V. Nicosia, V. Latora, Structural measures for multiplex networks, *Physical Review E* 89 (3) (2014) 032804.

- [22] S. Gomez, A. Diaz-Guilera, J. Gomez-Gardenes, C. J. Perez-Vicente, Y. Moreno, A. Arenas, Diffusion dynamics on multiplex networks, *Physical review letters* 110 (2) (2013) 028701.
- [23] M. De Domenico, C. Granell, M. A. Porter, A. Arenas, The physics of spreading processes in multilayer networks, *Nature Physics* 12 (10) (2016) 901–906.
- [24] C. Granell, S. Gómez, A. Arenas, Dynamical interplay between awareness and epidemic spreading in multiplex networks, *Physical review letters* 111 (12) (2013) 128701.
- [25] J. Sanz, C.-Y. Xia, S. Meloni, Y. Moreno, Dynamics of interacting diseases, *Physical Review X* 4 (4) (2014) 041005.
- [26] V. Gemmetto, D. Garlaschelli, Multiplexity versus correlation: the role of local constraints in real multiplexes, *Scientific reports* 5 (2015) 9120.
- [27] V. Nicosia, V. Latora, Measuring and modeling correlations in multiplex networks, *Physical Review E* 92 (3) (2015) 032805.
- [28] C. Zhong, H.-w. Chang, D. Karamshuk, D. Lee, N. Sastry, Wearing many (social) hats: How different are your different social network personae?, in: *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, Vol. 11, 2017.
- [29] J. Baumgartner, S. Zannettou, B. Keegan, M. Squire, J. Blackburn, The pushshift reddit dataset, in: *Proceedings of the International AAAI Conference on Web and Social Media*, Vol. 14, 2020, pp. 830–839.
- [30] J. N. Cummings, J. B. Lee, R. E. Kraut, Communication technology and friendship during the transition from high school to college. (2006).
- [31] S. G. Roberts, R. I. Dunbar, Communication in social networks: Effects of kinship, network size, and emotional closeness, *Personal Relationships* 18 (3) (2011) 439–452.
- [32] K. Ollivier, C. Boldrini, A. Passarella, M. Conti, Structural invariants in individuals language use: The “ego network” of words, in: S. Aref, K. Bontcheva, M. Braghieri, F. Dignum, F. Giannotti, F. Grisolia, D. Pedreschi (Eds.), *Social Informatics*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2020, pp. 267–282.

- [33] D. Comaniciu, P. Meer, Mean shift: A robust approach toward feature space analysis, *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 24 (5) (2002) 603–619.
- [34] V. Arnaboldi, A. Passarella, M. Conti, R. I. Dunbar, *Online social networks: human cognitive constraints in Facebook and Twitter personal graphs*, Elsevier, 2015.
- [35] P. Paraskevopoulos, C. Boldrini, A. Passarella, M. Conti, The academic wanderer: structure of collaboration network and relation with research performance, *Applied Network Science* In press (2021) 37.